

Well	ExptType	Experiment	Sample	TargetType	Target	Status	Concentration	Supermix	CopiesPer20uLWell
A07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
A08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	OK	2.3	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	46
C07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
C08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	OK	1.8	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	36
D07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
D08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	OK	1014	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	20280
E07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
E08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6	OK	1.5	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	30
A09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
A10	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B10	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	0.7	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	14
C09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	0.66	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	13.2
C10	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
D09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
D10	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
E09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
E10	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	

TotalConfMax	TotalConfMin	PoissonConfMax	PoissonConfMin	Positives	Negatives	Ch1+Ch2+	Ch1+Ch2-	Ch1-Ch2+	Ch1-Ch2-	Linkage	AcceptedDroplets
				48	13479						13527
				0	16626						16626
				0	12488						12488
		3.2	1.5	28	14606						14634
				40	12727						12767
		2.7	1.1	21	13689						13710
				7512	6044						13556
		1036	993	8992	6572						15564
				41	14273						14314
		2.3	0.9	19	15047						15066
				0	15869						15869
				0	14178						14178
				12	8189						8201
		1.27	0.33	9	15114						15123
		1.2	0.32	9	15939						15948
				0	15455						15455
				13985	104						14089
				13002	96						13098
				0	15295						15295
				0	15932						15932

PoissonFractionalAbundanceMin	ReferenceAssayNumber	TargetAssayNumber	Threshold	MeanAmplitudeofPositives	MeanAmplitudeofNegatives
	1	1	8932	9995.9	8039.5
	1	1	0	0	6470.7
	1	1	0	0	8257.9
	1	1	8619	10268	7699.8
	1	1	8349	9077	7604.4
	1	1	7919	8645.1	7039.8
	1	1	11087	14318	8421.9
	1	1	10738	14520	7819.7
	1	1	8508	9357.6	7632
	1	1	7966	9552	6934.9
	1	1	0	0	4262.6
	1	1	0	0	3781
	1	1	5328	7301.9	4445
	1	1	5242	16630	4548.4
	1	1	4993	9827.4	4321.2
	1	1	0	0	4075.5
	1	1	10392	26542	4642.7
	1	1	16875	26675	6614.9
	1	1	0	0	4292.5
	1	1	0	0	4064.8

MeanAmplitudeTotal	ExperimentComments	MergedWells	TotalConfMax68	TotalConfMin68	PoissonConfMax68	PoissonConfMin68
8046.4	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
6470.7	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
8257.9	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
7704.7	Absolute Quantification Experiment				2.71	1.85
7609	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
7042.3	Absolute Quantification Experiment				2.23	1.44
11689	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
11691	Absolute Quantification Experiment				1025	1003
7637	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
6938.2	Absolute Quantification Experiment				1.85	1.17
4262.6	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
3781	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
4449.2	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
4555.6	Absolute Quantification Experiment				0.96	0.49
4324.3	Absolute Quantification Experiment				0.91	0.47
4075.5	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
26380	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
26528	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
4292.5	Absolute Quantification Experiment					
4064.8	Absolute Quantification Experiment					

